

BUILDING IMMUNITY AGAINST CORRUPTION IN STUDENTS THROUGH THE LIBRARY

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Abstract. *This article has covered the issue of building immunity against corruption through reading books. Today, scientific and artistic literature plays an important role in expanding human thinking, strengthening the moral position and forming stable attitudes against corruption. The article analyzes the mechanisms of forming a stable negative attitude to corruption in the younger generation through the process of reading books, the role of literature in raising the legal awareness of students. The President of our country's resolution No PQ 228 "On measures to introduce a system of continuous improvement of knowledge of the population and public servants in the field of combating corruption" was also analyzed.*

Keywords: *corruption, fight against corruption, corruption immunity, legal culture, moral immunity, legal awareness, reading culture, critical thinking, legal literacy, education of students and psychology of corruption.*

Introduction

Corruption is the unlawful use of a person's position or office for the purpose of obtaining a material or immaterial benefit in his own interests or in the interests of other persons, as well as the unlawful provision of such benefit [1]. Global studies show that legal measures alone are not enough to fight corruption and build immunity against it. In this regard, the legal culture, ethical standards and social activism of citizens play a decisive role. In particular, through the education system, especially by creating a culture of reading among students, it is possible to build immunity in their minds against corruption.

In the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-228 of June 21, 2024; On measures to introduce a system of continuous improvement of knowledge of the population and public servants in the field of combating corruption, we can also see the processes of building immunity against corruption based on obtaining information on corruption in the process of reading books. In particular: raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population and civil servants, forming legal immunity in society against corruption, inculcating the values of honesty in the minds of the younger generation; continuous improvement of knowledge, skills and qualifications of employees in positions of public service responsible for combating corruption and those with high corruption risks; assessment and certification of the knowledge of civil servants in the field of combating corruption and maintenance of a register of certified civil servants; maintenance of an electronic database of national and foreign experience, scientific, methodological and practical developments, achievements in the field of combating corruption; implementation of scientific research programs and projects on topical problems of combating corruption, including with the involvement of national and international grants.

In addition, within the framework of the Global Resource for Anti-Corruption Education and Empowerment of Youth (GRACE) program:

to take measures to attract foreign investments, grants and sponsorship in order to create high-quality multiplication films, video and audio materials;

translation of educational materials into the state language (dubbing of film, video and audio materials) and placement in the Virtual Academy.

It is stipulated that the Virtual Academy should organize the educational process in the field of anti-corruption, including the development of curricula and programs and the placement of information about courses in the Virtual Academy [1]. In addition, within the framework of the Global Resource for Anti-Corruption Education and Youth Empowerment (GRACE) program, implemented on the initiative of the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, it is necessary to implement systematic measures aimed at forming an anti-corruption culture and strengthening the principles of honesty and integrity in the minds of young people. In this direction, first of all, it is advisable to convey anti-corruption knowledge to the general public, especially to the youth audience, in a simple, understandable and effective form by creating high-quality animated films, videos and audio materials based on modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies.

At the same time, in the process of developing these media products, it is necessary to develop mechanisms for attracting foreign investment, participating in international and national grant programs, as well as mobilizing sponsorship donations based on the principles of social responsibility. In this regard, expanding cooperation on the basis of public-private partnerships, launching integrated projects with international organizations, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and scientific and educational institutions will be of great importance. Diversifying financial resources will ensure the sustainability and quality of the content created.

Translation of educational materials into the state language, in particular, professional dubbing of animated films, videos and audio materials and their adaptation to the national mentality and cultural values is an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of education. In the translation process, terminological accuracy, correct interpretation of legal concepts and preservation of the scientific method should be ensured. It is also advisable to form an open and continuous educational environment by systematizing the adapted materials in digital format and placing them on the Virtual Academy platform.

Within the framework of the Virtual Academy, it is required to comprehensively organize the educational process in the field of combating corruption, that is, to develop curricula and programs based on a modern competency-based approach, to form courses based on a modular system, to introduce elements of distance learning, to develop interactive tests and assessment criteria. Also, publishing detailed annotations, goals and objectives, learning outcomes, methodological materials used and assessment criteria for each course on the Virtual Academy platform ensures transparency and openness of the educational process.

In addition, it is necessary to implement mechanisms for monitoring user activity, forming an analytical database, assessing the effectiveness of training courses, and regularly updating content within the platform. The introduction of digital educational resources will serve to disseminate knowledge and skills in the field of combating corruption to the general public, improve the legal culture of young people, and form an uncompromising attitude towards corruption in society

The socio-psychological roots of corruption can be traced back to:

1. Self-interest and needs (related to Maslow's hierarchy of needs). The American psychologist A. Maslow's pyramid of needs states that humans primarily seek to satisfy

physiological and security needs. If these needs are not fully satisfied, there are instances of attempts to solve some needs by illegal means, i.e. by intervening in corruption [2]. For example, a low-paid public servant may be tempted to accept a bribe in order to meet family financial needs. Putting self-interest above the public good creates an environment of corruption. This shows that the root of corruption is not individual needs, but social inequality and unequal distribution.

2. Indifference in the social environment: In an environment where corruption is accepted as a social norm, the mechanisms to combat it are weakened [3]. When there is a general indifference to corruption among citizens, when the stereotype is strong that "everyone does it", it becomes widespread. People start to accept it as normal to take or give a bribe, and they start to act like that. For example, instead of taking a test to get a driver's license legally, most people think it's a simple matter to get a license through bribery or dating. As long as there are no objections or legal grounds, this behavior becomes entrenched in the public mind as a normal norm. Social indifference is not just indifference, it's also passive indifference. The French philosopher Voltaire's idea that "evil comes not only from the wicked, but also from the silent" illustrates the importance of direct participation of society in the fight against corruption.

3. The erosion of moral standards; as our First President pointed out, a spiritually strong people cannot be defeated by external enemies, on the contrary, a society without spirituality will suffer internal decay and will be in a self-destructive state. This reflects the importance of the role of spirituality in the development and sustainability of society [4]. The moral crisis is when self-interest is put before shared values. As a person no longer values honesty, conscience, justice, he evaluates his actions not from the point of view of the law and society, but only from the point of view of profit.

4. Low legal literacy. Weak legal culture and civic awareness leads to a lack of acceptance of corrupt behavior as a crime [5]. In order to fight corruption, a person must know his rights and obligations, as well as the responsibility for corrupt actions. When legal literacy is low, people don't recognize a corrupt act, they don't see it as a crime. In the fight against this disease, the leading role is played by the inner culture of the individual, his mental position and moral immunity.

The book is one of the most effective sources for shaping the human mind. Ethical, legal, historical and literary literature in particular can be a powerful tool in forming a negative attitude towards corruption in readers. This process should be carried out in the following directions:

Building moral immunity in the students. Moral immunity can be boosted through literature. For example, through the novel "Days Gone By", young people understand the vital importance of justice and fairness. The heroes of the play, their lives on the path of honesty and corruption, teach the reader a profound lesson. This will help students build their own immunity to injustice and corruption, and give them a broader understanding of what it means to fight injustice and corruption.

Formation of legal awareness and sense of responsibility in students. Academic and legal literature (e.g. laws, resolutions and decrees on combating corruption, international conventions) provides readers with an understanding of the structure of the state, its functions and consequences of corruption, and allows them to understand the extent to which corruption can destroy the state.

Formation of social analysis and critical thinking skills in students. Publicist and analytical literature helps the younger generation to analyze the real situation in society, to understand justice, to protest and to form a civic position, how to react in the face of corruption.

Approaches to build immunity against corruption in students include:

The historical and pedagogical approach. Through historical literature, including "The Traps of Temur" and "Sahihi Bukhari", historical figures teach how to implement the principles of just governance and how to earn an honest living, and how not to betray anyone's right. This, along with historical pride and the desire for justice, will reinforce the desire for a just and honest life in the minds of young people.

Implementation of spiritual education through artistic works. In literature classes, analyzing works that reveal current topics related to corruption, engaging students in debate, allowing students to clearly visualize how corruption will affect the future, will create a broader view of corruption.

Educate students in legal literacy. In schools and universities, students are educated about the rule of law, legal responsibility and the consequences of corruption through subjects such as "Basics of legal culture", "Civil society" and "State and legal bases". Develop critical thinking and self-awareness skills. Teaching students to analyze corruption cases and propose alternative solutions develops their critical thinking skills.

In conclusion, corruption is a complex socio-legal phenomenon that poses a serious threat to the development of society, and its roots are not only in legal gaps, but also in the spiritual and moral world of the individual, the social environment and the level of legal literacy. Global experience and national research shows that the fight against corruption should not be limited to punitive and supervisory mechanisms. On the contrary, continuous education, legal culture, moral education and social activism are important for the formation of sustainable immunity to corruption in society. The process of building immunity against corruption requires the close cooperation of the educational system, the family, society and the state. Only if each person actively participates in the fight against corruption through his legal knowledge, moral position and civic responsibility, the intolerant attitude to this evil will be established in society. As a result, a strong foundation will be created to build a fair, transparent and sustainable society.

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